

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Algebraik-giperbolok natural splayn va D^m splayn

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Ma'lumki, splaynlar nazariyasi rivojlanishi I.J.Schonbergning [1] maqolasida keltirilgan kubik splaynlarning $L_2^{(2)}$ fazosidagi funksiya normasining kvadratiga minimum beruvchi variatsion masala yechimi bilan bog'liqligi ko'rsatuvchi D.Holladay [2] maqolasiga borib taqaladi. Dastlabki sistematik splaynlar nazariyasi J.H.Ahlberg, E.Nilson, J.Walsh lar tomonidan [3] adabiyotda keltirilgan.

Ushbu ishda $L_2^{(m)}(0,1)$ fazosidagi normani minimallashtiruvchi D^m splayn va $K_{2,y}^m$ fazolaridagi normalarni minimallashtiruvchi algebraik-giperbolik natural splaynlarning funksiyalarni yaqinlashtirishdagi xatoliklarini $m = 2, 3, 4$ hollarida taqqoslaymiz.

Dastlab, $L_2^{(m)}(0,1)$ va $K_{2,y}^m$ Gilbert fazolari ta'riflari va undagi normalarni minimallashtiruvchi splayn funksiyalarni keltiramiz.

Ushbu $L_2^{(m)}(0,1)$ $-m - 1$ tartibgacha hosilalalari uzluksiz va m tartibli hosilasi kvadarati bilan integralanuvchi funksiyalar sinfi quyidagi skalayar ko'paytma bilan faktorizatsya qilingan Gilbert fazosini tashkil qiladi.

$$(\varphi, \psi)_{L_2^{(m)}(0,1)} = \int_0^1 \varphi^{(m)} \psi^{(m)} dx$$

Ushbu fazoda norma skalyar ko'paytma yordamida quyidagicha kiritiladi

$$\|f\|_{L_2^{(m)}(0,1)} = \left(\int_0^1 (f^{(m)}(x))^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Ushbu (1) normaga minimum beruvchi spalyinni D^m spalyin deb nomlaymiz. D^m splayn $P_{m-1}(x)$ funkisylarga aniq va quyidagi ko'rinishda aniqlanadi

$$S_m(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N C_i G(x - x_i) + \sum_{\alpha=0}^{m-1} p_\alpha x^\alpha$$

Bu yerda, $C_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1), p_\alpha (\alpha = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1)$ lar D^m spalyinning koeffissientlari va ular [4] ishda berilgan.

II. Ushbu $K_{2,y}^m(0,1)$ $m - 1$ tartibgacha hosilalalari uzluksiz va m tartibli hosilasi kvadarati bilan integralanuvchi funksiyalar sinfi quyidagi skalyar ko'paytma bilan fazktorizatsya qilingan Gilbert fazo tashkil qiladi.

$$(\varphi, \psi)_{K_{2,y}^m(0,1)} = \int_0^1 (\varphi^{(m)} - \nu^2 \varphi^{(m-2)}) (\psi^{(m)} - \nu^2 \psi^{(m-2)}) dx \quad (2)$$

ushbu fazoda norma skalyar ko'paytma orqali kiritiladi.

$$\|\varphi\|_{K_{2,y}^m(0,1)} = \left(\int_0^1 (\varphi^{(m)} - \nu^2 \varphi^{(m-2)})^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Ushbu (2) normaga minimum beruvchi spalyzni algebraik-giperbolik spalyzn deb ataymiz. Algebraik-giperbolik spalyzn $\sinh \nu x, \cosh \nu x$,

$$P_{m-3}(x)$$

funksyalarga aniq va quyidagi ko'rinishda aniqlanadi.

$$S_{\Delta m}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N C_i G(x - x_i) + d_1 \sinh(\nu x) + d_2 \cosh(\nu x) + \sum_{\alpha=0}^{m-3} p_\alpha x^\alpha$$

Bu yerda, $C_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, N), p_\alpha (\alpha = 0, 1, \dots, m - 3)$ lar algebraik giperbolik natural spalyning koeffisientlari va ular $m = 2, 3, 4$ hollarida mos ravishda [5,6,7] ishlarda berilgan. 1. $f_1 = \tan(x)$ funksyani algebraik-giperbolik natural spalyzn va D^m spalyzn orqali yaqinlashtirgandagi xatoliklar.

$f_1(x) = \tan(x)$							
	Taranglik koeffisienti	N=10			N=50		
		m=2	m=3	m=4	m=2	m=3	m=4
$R_n(f_1)_{K_{2,y}^{(m)}}$	$\nu = 0,1$	5,0(-3)	1,0(-3)	3,0(-4)	2,0(-4)	1,0(-5)	9,0(-7)
	$\nu = 1$	4,0(-3)	1,0(-3)	3,0(-4)	1,6(-4)	1,0(-5)	9,0(-7)
	$\nu = 2$	2,0(-3)	8,0(-4)	3,0(-4)	8,0(-5)	8,0(-6)	8,0(-7)
	$\nu = 3$	1,6(-3)	4,0(-4)	2,0(-4)	6,0(-5)	5,0(-6)	7,0(-7)
	$\nu = 4$	7,0(-3)	3,0(-4)	1,0(-4)	2,0(-4)	3,0(-6)	5,0(-7)
	$\nu = 10$	6,0(-2)	6,0(-3)	8,0(-4)	2,0(-3)	6,0(-4)	1,0(-6)
	$\nu = 15$	1,5(-1)	1,6(-2)	2,0(-3)	6,0(-3)	1,5(-4)	5,0(-6)
$R_n(f_1)_{L_2^{(m)}}$		5,0(-2)	1,0(-2)	3,0(-4)	2,0(-4)	1,0(-5)	9,0(-7)

2. $f_2 = e^5 x$ funksyani algebraik-giperbolik natural spalyzn va D^m spalyzn orqali yaqinlashtirgandagi xatoliklar.

$f_2(x) = e^{5x}$							
	Taranglik koeffisienti	N=10			N=50		
		m=2	m=3	m=4	m=2	m=3	m=4
$R_n(f_2)_{L_2^{(m)}}$	$\nu = 0,1$	1,6	0,4	1,0(-1)	7,0(-1)	3,0(-3)	2,0(-4)
	$\nu = 1$	1,6	0,4	1,0(-1)	6,0(-2)	3,0(-3)	2,0(-4)
	$\nu = 2$	1,0	0,3	8,0(-2)	6,0(-2)	3,0(-3)	1,8(-4)
	$\nu = 3$	1,0	0,2	6,0(-2)	4,0(-2)	2,0(-3)	1,0(-4)
	$\nu = 4$	0,6	0,1	3,0(-2)	2,0(-2)	1,0(-3)	8,0(-5)
	$\nu = 5$	1,0(-42)	1,0(-36)	3,0(-32)	7,0(-38)	8,0(-30)	4,0(-22)
	$\nu = 6$	7,0(-1)	1,8(-1)	4,0(-2)	3,0(-2)	1,6(-3)	1,0(-4)
	$\nu = 10$	5,0	1,0	3,0(-1)	2,0(-1)	1,0(-2)	6,0(-4)
	$\nu = 15$	10,0	3,0	7,0(-1)	5,0(-1)	3,0(-2)	1,8(-3)
$R_n(f_2)_{L_2^{(m)}}$		1,6	0,4	0,1	0,7	3,0(-3)	2,0(-4)

Berilgan jadvallarda, $R_n(f)$ bu $[0, 1]$ oraliqda berilgan funksiyalar bilan D^m , algebraik-giperbolik splaynlar orasidagi xatoliklarning maksimalidir. Yuqoridagi jadvallardan shuni xulosa qilamizki: ma'lum bir oraliqda uzluksiz bo'lgan funksiyalarni algebraik-giperbolik natural splayn bilan yaqinlashtirgandagi absolyut xatoliklarni taranglik koeffisientini o'zgartirish yordamida yaxshilash mumkin. Natijada, funksiyalarni algebraik-giperbolik natural splayn bilan yaqinlashtirganda yaqinlashish xatoligi taaranglik koeffisientining ma'lum qiymatlarida, D^m splayn, xususan $m = 3$ bo'lganda kubik splayn, bilan yaqinlashtirgandagi absolyut xatoliklaridan kichkina ekanligini kuzatamiz. Ko'plab amaliy masalalarda kubik splayn orqali yaqinlashtirishdan foydalaniladi, yuqoridagi natijalardan ko'rinadiki, algebraik-giperbolik natural splaynni amaliy masalalarga qo'llash orqali olingan natijalarni yanada yaxshilash mumkin.

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